

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

THE EFFECT OF THE PHYSICAL STATE OF THE SUBSTANCE ON THE THERAPEUTIC EFFICACY OF DRUGS

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Abstract

In recent years, several directions of biopharmaceutical research have been identified in pharmacy: studying the role of pharmaceutical factors, absorption conditions, biotransformation, biological affinity and its determination methods, development of methods for identifying drugs in biological fluids, investigation of drug pharmacokinetics, and determination of clinical effects.

One of the main objectives of biopharmaceutics is to study the physical state of substances, which plays a crucial role in the therapeutic significance of drugs. In the past, insufficient attention was given to the physical state of substances during the development, production, and prescription of drugs. However, experimental clinical studies have revealed that the effectiveness, absorption, distribution in the body and tissues, and concentration of a drug depend on the type of dosage form, administration route, and the physical properties of its components. This is because the physicochemical state of a drug substance significantly affects its biological activity. From a biopharmaceutical perspective, the physical state of a substance includes polymorphism, particle size, aggregate state, crystal form, and surface properties of raw materials, which are justified by electrophysical, optical, and other characteristics. These factors can be the cause of the therapeutic non-equivalence of drug formulations or their adverse effects. The physicochemical state of a drug substance significantly affects its biological activity. Therefore, research in this field is essential and highly important.

Keywords: biopharmaceutics, drug substance, pharmaceutical factor, therapeutic efficacy, physical state.

Biopharmaceutics studies and investigates in detail the biological effects of pharmaceutical preparations depending on their physicochemical properties, form, and manufacturing technology. The study of the impact of technological factors on the biological activity of drugs is associated with the names of Lewis and Wagner (USA). These factors have become the object of study for a new scientific discipline. Biopharmaceutics emerged from the necessity to understand and investigate the biological reactions caused by pharmaceutical preparations in the body, as well as the processes leading to the formation of their metabolites.

Pharmacy ensures the preparation of specific pharmaceutical forms from medicinal substances. For this purpose, drug substances are ground, dissolved, mixed, and processed into various dosage forms. Different excipients, mechanical methods, machines, and equipment are used in this process.

During these processes, certain biological effects can be enhanced, while others can be weakened or even completely eliminated. The study of these changes, processes, and factors and their impact on the therapeutic effect of pharmaceutical preparations constitutes the primary task of biopharmaceutics. Drugs developed based on biopharmaceutical research results have minimal side effects.

In modern times, several directions of biopharmaceutical research have been identified:

- Studying the role of pharmaceutical factors
- Absorption conditions
- Biotransformation
- Biological affinity and its determination methods
- Development of methods for identifying drugs in biological fluids
- Investigation of drug pharmacokinetics
- Determination of clinical effects

One of the main objectives of biopharmaceutics is to study the physical state of substances, which plays a crucial role in the therapeutic significance of drugs.

The physical state of a substance from a biopharmaceutical perspective includes:

- Polymorphism
- Particle size
- Aggregate state
- Crystal form
- Electrophysical, optical, and other characteristics that justify the surface properties of raw materials and may be the cause of therapeutic non-equivalence or adverse effects of pharmaceutical preparations.

Polymorphism is the ability of a substance to form multiple crystalline structures that are chemically identical.

tical but differ in physical properties. For example, carbon exists in different crystalline structures, such as graphite and coal. Many organic substances, including pharmaceuticals, can form crystalline structures. Polymorphism is observed in salicylates, barbiturates, sulfonamides, antibiotics, hormones, and others. For instance, acetylsalicylic acid exists in six crystalline forms, while cortisone acetate has five. Most modifications do not have specific names and are designated by letters (α , β , γ , etc.) or numbers (I, II, III, etc.).

The formation of a specific crystalline modification depends on the complex conditions in which synthesis and separation from natural raw materials occur, particularly the crystallization conditions of the substance (temperature, solvent nature, pressure).

Polymorphic changes in pharmaceutical substances can occur not only during their synthesis, purification, and drying but also during drug formulation. These changes can take place during the preparation of suspensions and solutions, solvent replacement, grinding of softened pharmaceutical substances, mixing and triturating of drugs and excipients (especially in the presence of moisture), drying of softened powders or granular mixtures, as well as during wet granulation, tablet compression, coating, melting of bases and their freezing, suspension preparation, dissolution in hydrophilic and emulsion bases, and more.

Metastable modifications formed under these conditions can easily create homogeneous systems. For example, during storage, solutions may transform into more stable modifications that form less soluble homogeneous systems (suspensions). This applies to mixtures, injection solutions, ointments, and creams. The formation of unexpected crystals may lead to product degradation or the emergence of properties not specified in the product instructions.

Polymorphic transformations are commonly observed in the preparation of drugs containing solid fats, such as ointments, pastes, and suppositories. This also applies to cocoa butter polymorphism. Cocoa butter consists primarily of triglycerides of oleic, stearic, and palmitic acids. It has four polymorphic modifications (α , β , β' , and γ) with different melting points (18°C, 24°C, 28–31°C, and 34–35°C), cooling temperatures, specific gravity, etc. These factors must be considered when preparing suppositories using the casting method.

Different polymorphic modifications of the same substance have varying solubility, melting points, oxidation resistance, and stability against destructive processes. Consequently, they differ in absorption rates and stability within pharmaceutical forms.

Typically, stable polymorphic modifications of drug substances exhibit better solubility and higher absorption rates. For instance, among the three polymorphic forms of vitamin B1, the metastable modification (1200 mg) dissolves in 1:1 distilled water, whereas the stable modification (60 mg) is significantly less soluble. Additionally, the metastable modification ensures higher bioavailability and higher vitamin concentration in the bloodstream. Similar phenomena are observed in acetylsalicylic acid, norsulfazole, and other substances.

The dependence of polymorphism on external conditions allows pharmaceutical technology to rationally utilize technological methods and excipients to control polymorphic transformations. By directing these transformations appropriately, researchers can obtain modifications with higher solubility, activity, and stability. Scientific studies in this direction help identify new patterns in the relationship between drug substances and excipients in complex physicochemical systems.

The optical, electrophysical, and other properties of pharmaceutical substances significantly influence the degree of their pharmacological activity. For example, there is no chemical difference between optical isomers, yet each rotates the plane of polarized light in opposite directions. Therefore, chemical analysis can prove the presence of a substance in a drug preparation with 100% certainty. However, this does not necessarily mean that the substance will exhibit the necessary therapeutic effect. For instance, the left-rotating isomer of levomycetin is twice as active as the racemic mixture known as synthomycin, and the left-rotating isomer of propylnoradrenaline is 800 times more active than its right-rotating isomer.

The degree of ionization of a substance plays a crucial role in its passage through lipid barriers (such as the stomach and intestinal walls). Depending on the pH, pharmaceutical substances can exist in either ionized or non-ionized forms. The concentration of hydrogen ions also influences solubility, the partition coefficient of the drug, membrane potential, and surface activity.

Drugs characterized by anhydrous forms or the presence of crystalline hydrates dissolve and absorb at different rates, which naturally affects their bioeffectiveness and therapeutic efficiency. For example, the anhydrous modifications of theophylline, caffeine, ampicillin, and others dissolve faster, absorb more completely, and ensure higher plasma concentrations compared to their corresponding crystalline hydrates.

The dispersibility and particle size of pharmaceutical substances influence not only technological aspects (such as powder material dispersion, flowability, mixing uniformity, and dosing accuracy) but also the rate and completeness of absorption, except in intravenous administration. The degree of particle size reduction determines the absorption rate of pharmaceutical substances, especially poorly soluble compounds. Biopharmaceutical studies have established the pharmacotherapeutic significance of particle size reduction for antibiotics, sulfonamides, salicylates, steroids, furan derivatives, and others. This has necessitated improvements in technological processes. Modern pharmaceutical manufacturing has incorporated micronization, which allows the production of particles smaller than 5 microns.

It is well known that the solubility of any substance depends on its particle size and surface area. The smaller the particle size and the larger the total surface area, the faster the substance dissolves and becomes available for absorption. For example, if norgestrel (an oral contraceptive) is micronized to a particle size of 3.7 microns, 1 mg of the substance will consist of

135,000 particles, and a single dose (30 mg) will contain 4.05 million particles. In contrast, simple grinding to a particle size of 100 microns results in only 7 particles per milligram of norgestrel, and a single dose will contain only 210 particles. Therefore, micronized substances dissolve and absorb significantly faster than those subjected to conventional grinding. By using micronized substances, the required dose of drugs such as griseofulvin, digoxin, and acetylsalicylic acid can be reduced while maintaining the necessary therapeutic effect.

It has been determined that when sulfadimezine is administered as a conventional powder, the maximum blood concentration of sulfonamide is reached two hours earlier than usual. In this case, the peak concentration of the micronized substance is 40% higher, and the total amount of absorbed sulfonamide is 20% greater than that of the non-micronized powder. Additionally, by achieving the molecular dispersion of griseofulvin in polyvinylpyrrolidone, the bioavailability of this antibiotic was increased by 7 to 11 times compared to its micronized form.

The degree of particle size reduction can also influence adverse effects. For example, acetylsalicylic acid can cause gastrointestinal bleeding. Comparative studies have shown that larger crystalline powder (with particle sizes around 1680 microns) in gelatin capsules causes more frequent and intense bleeding than finer powder (with particle sizes around 125 microns). This is explained by the faster dissolution of the smaller particles in the stomach, leading to less irritation of the mucous membrane.

However, in some cases, reducing particle size can decrease the therapeutic activity and stability of the drug. For example, increasing the particle size of penicillin and erythromycin significantly reduces their activity when taken orally. This occurs because their hydrolytic degradation accelerates, and their stability decreases in the presence of digestive fluids. This is due to a sharp increase in the surface contact of the drug

with biological fluids. Such observations have led to precise regulations on particle size in pharmaceutical standards and technical documentation.

The dependence of a drug's bioavailability on the dispersibility of its active substances in ointments has led to the introduction of clearer microscopic methods for measuring particle volume.

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